

YOUTHS AND CRIMES IN EKET SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined the criminal practices among youths in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to identify the type of criminal activities practised by youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State and to identify the rates of criminal practices among youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. A survey research design was adopted by the researcher for the fact-finding. The research made use of both primary and secondary data. Routine Activity (RA) theory was adopted for the study. A simple random sampling technique was adopted in the distribution of the questionnaire which was distributed to 400 respondents. Data collected were analysed using charts through the use of Microsoft Office 2010. Findings revealed that the youths in Eket Senatorial District mostly engage in burglary, armed robbery, assault, kidnapping, murder and rape. People of Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State experience more assault than any other crime. From the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that the government should equip the Nigerian Police and other security organizations for effective crime policing in Nigeria, the government should encourage private sector expansion to have more job creation for the teaming unemployed youths found within every region of the nation, and government should improve the economic condition of the nation to bring about improved standard of living for the masses.

KEYWORDS: Youths, Crime, Eket, and Akwa Ibom State

INTRODUCTION

The entire world is faced with various kinds of crime, no human society is completely free from crime-related challenges. However, the patterns, magnitude and degree of manifestation of criminal activities differ in different societies across the globe (Femi *et al*, 2015). Crime has become a concern of crime because it is a social problem; it is like an epidemic disease that attacks the rights of individuals and groups. Crime has generated a hot debate in the agenda of most nations, yet it does not seem to be on the decline, rather it is on the increase (Esiri, 2016). According to Esiri (2016), crime rates are much higher in cities than in rural areas and this has been the trend for several centuries. Crime is one of the human

security problems confronting humanity across the world, nations have grappled to contain the rising incidence of homicide, armed robbery, kidnap, drug trafficking, sex trafficking, illegal gun-running and a host of others (Nwankwo and James, 2016). United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime in 2011 reported that homicides globally were estimated at 468,000 and more than a third (36%) was estimated to have occurred in Africa, 31% in the Americas, 27% in Asia, 5% in Europe and 1% in the tropical Pacific region (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Crime has become a hot debate in the agenda of most nations yet it does not seem to be on the decline, rather it is on the increase (Esiri, 2016). There is no universal definition of crime, and this is a result of changes in social, political, psychological and economic conditions (Femi *et al.*, 2015). The definition or conception of crime is based on offences being committed against the citizens of a country or its sets of rule and regulations (Omoyibo, 2012). The value system of a society defines what is criminal and as a result, the rate, type, cause, and effect on each society or community may differ widely (Esiri, 2016). Crime has been defined in various ways Marshall and Clark (1952) cited in Esiri, (2016), defined crime as “any act or omission prohibited by public law for the protection of the public and punishable by state in a judicial proceeding in its name.” Tappan (1960) cited in Esiri (2016) defined crime as “an instrumental act or omission in violation of criminal law, committed without justification and sanctioned by the state as felony or misdemeanour.” Again, Clinard (1974) cited in Esiri (2016) wrote that crime refers to those activities which break the law of the land and are subject to official punishment after conviction. Crime is now a global phenomenon to which all towns and cities are susceptible (Kinsella, 2012).

Crime is at an alarming rate in Nigeria, and many factors are contributing to this anti-societal behaviour both among the youths and adults in our society today (Femi *et al.*, 2015). In Nigeria, crime manifests in the convulsive upsurge of both violent and non-violent crimes (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Incidents of armed robbery, assassination and ransom-driven kidnapping are now ravaging the polity like a tsunami and spreading a climate of fears and anxieties about public safety. The upsurge of crime has been ongoing as Nigeria has been on the global crime map since the 1980s (Nwankwo and James, 2016). These throes of crime for decades are traceable to poverty, poor parental upbringing, and greed amongst the youth; a get-rich-quick mentality, and an inadequate crime control model of national security among others. Crime portrays the inability of the government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives, properties and the conduct of economic activities considering the alarming increase in criminal activities in Nigeria such as armed robbery, terrorism and other related crimes (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

The economic situation of the nation has put pressure on the survival of Nigerians especially the youths which form the majority of the populace. Many Nigerian youths today are looking for different ways to survive, and a portion of this populace who cannot reach the moral belief of dignity of good labour have taken to various forms of criminal activities as a means of livelihood among the various parts of Nigeria. Many social, political and cultural factors also contribute to the rise of crime and criminal activities in Nigeria today. Among these factors are; that Nigerian society places great emphasis on material wealth and as a result, its youths are becoming prone to deviant behaviour which is the first step away from the accepted norms of a society or an institution. Urbanization, the worship of money rather than honour and achievement, as well as the false desire to live and spend rich as a rich man syndrome, have been named amongst others as causes of crime in Nigeria. Incidents of

internet theft, armed robbery, assassination and ransom-driven kidnapping are now ravaging the polity like a tsunami and spreading a climate of fears and anxieties about public safety (Emeh, 2011).

The Akwa Ibom people are known for their hard work. In the southern part of Nigeria, hard work is a commendable cultural practice and belief among the Akwa Ibom people. Despite this moral cultural element of the Akwa Ibom people, and just like any part of the nation, and the world at large, part of the populace in this part of the world chose to deviate from the societal moral code and venture into various forms of criminal practices as a way of life and survival. The Akwa Ibom people are known to be hard-working. This hard-working character of the people has provided many opportunities for Akwa Ibom youths in Akwa Ibom State to earn their living without getting involved in crimes and criminal practices. A lot of Akwa Ibom youths have become financially independent through rightful business engagement in various markets. Despite these opportunities offered by the markets, some Akwa Ibom youths still believe that living or making earnings from crimes and criminal activities should be their life path.

It is important to note that the people of Eket Senatorial District have witnessed different forms of crimes and criminal activities carried out by the youths of the senatorial district in Akwa Ibom State. These criminal activities vary with place, time and persons involved. As related to crime generally, the consequences of these practices affect the socio-economic, socio-political and socio-cultural relationships of the people in the district. The recent political activities in the area have contributed to the criminal activities among the district youths.

The recent economic hardship through the removal of fuel subsidies has forced many youths out of their comfort zones to hunt for survival. The quest for survival is one of human characteristics, and most of these youths have taken this responsibility in their own hands. But the questions remain; what type of work do they do for survival? How do their survival activities affect the peaceful co-existence of the people of Eket Senatorial District? And what are the efforts of the security operatives and citizens, which have been put in place to curb these activities which in some ways have become threats to the moral settings, acceptable norms and laws of the nation as expected to be upheld by the people of Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria as a nation? These questions form the identifiable gaps for the study within the study area which this study is set to examine the different criminal activities of the youths of Eket Senatorial District.

The main objective of this study is to examine the criminal practices among youths in Eket Senatorial District and proffer possible solutions in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general.

The specific objectives of the study include to:

1. identifying the type of criminal activities practised by youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State.
2. identifying the rates of criminal practices among youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Crimes and Criminal Activities in Nigeria

Nearly everywhere and around Nigerian cities, the atmosphere is inflicted with

criminal menace being wrecked on law-abiding members of the Nigerian public by criminals (Uyang, Festus, and Bassey, 2016). The highway has become a theatre for frequent robbers, car snatching and murder, while the homes of the rich and the poor are targets of daily murderous campaigns by hoodlums (Ushie, 2000). According to Esiri (2016), types of crime that have been identified in Nigeria range from petty – theft to violent crimes such as assault, kidnapping, murder and terrorism (in the most recent times). Crime in Nigeria occurs within contexts that are characterized by conflicts, political instability, extreme differences in economic well-being, uncertainty about the course of future events, and a shifting balance of formal and informal social control mechanisms (Uyang, Festus, and Bassey, 2016).

According to Emeh (2011), Nigeria's crime manifests in the convulsive upsurge of both violent and non-violent crimes. Dambazau (2007), posits that the upsurge of crime has been ongoing as Nigeria has been on the global crime map since the 1980s. These throes of crime for decades, according to Nwankwo and James (2016) are traceable to poverty, poor parental upbringing, and greed amongst the youth; get rich quick mentality, inadequate crime control model of national security among others. According to Osawe (2015), crime portrays the inability of the government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives, properties and the conduct of economic activities considering the alarming increase in criminal activities in Nigeria such as armed robbery, terrorism and other related crimes (Osawe, 2015). According to Nwankwo and James (2016), several causes of crime have been identified by scholars and social analysts. Notable among them is the availability of arms in the hands of illegal users, particularly civilians motivates criminality in Nigeria.

Hull, Evans, and Davis (2006) argued that the proliferation of arms contributes to conflict in two main ways namely: 'increasingly lethal firepower is likely to cause higher levels of destruction; and that augmentation of sophisticated weaponry creates a vicious cycle whereby competing militias engage in an arms race to gain dominance in capability (Hull, Evans, and Davis, 2006). Such competitions often result in violence. No zone in Nigeria is immune to crime. However, the frequency and fatality rate varies (Nwankwo and James, 2016). An analysis in a Nigeria Watch Third Report on Violence in Nigeria (2006-2011) not only acknowledged that the second main cause of violence in Nigeria is crime but reported its heavy presence in the South, especially in highly populated areas like Lagos and Port Harcourt. Nwankwo and James (2016), further maintain that fatalities in Nigeria are a result of major criminal activities including armed robbery, cultism, kidnapping, rape, domestic violence, assassination, thuggery and hooliganism. Nwankwo and James (2016) aver that crime relates to drug use which has social consequences on students manifesting in various forms including assassination, kidnapping, kidnapping, lack of interest in education, armed robbery and other criminal offences.

Major crimes in Nigeria include rape, kidnapping, murder, burglary, fraud, terrorism, robbery, cyber-crimes, bribery and corruption, money laundering and so on. According to the statistics released by the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics in 2016, Lagos, Abuja, Delta, Kano, Plateau, Ondo, Oyo, Bauchi, Adamawa and Gombe States made the top ten lists of states with a high number of crimes (Oguntunde, Ojo, Okagbue, and Oguntunde, 2018). Recent events of criminal activities also point to an urgent need for information to ameliorate peoples' anxiety about the threat posed by the galloping rate at which crimes are moving in Nigeria (Adetula, 2013).

According to Adetula (2013), the suggested security index of Nigeria by the

assessment of Index Crime (2012) indicated general lapses in the security situation of Nigeria with a percentage image tilting towards crime proneness with 67.51% while her safety opportunities put 32.49%. Also, reported was the 66.67% prediction of a total insecurity situation from the appraisal obtained from crimes for the past 3 years. Adetula further maintained that the list showed the percentage impacts and implications of insecurity on Nigerians and addressed these as follows: Worries over breaking into one's homes and stealing things 54.17%; worries of being mugged or robbed 75%; worries over a personal car being stolen 70.83%; worries over items in the car being stolen 75%; worries on personal physical attacks 62.50%; worries over being insulted 75%; worries of being subjected to a physical attack because of coloured skin, ethnic origin, or religion affiliation 45%; the problem of people using or dealing in drugs 90%; problem over property crimes such as vandalism and theft 75%; problem of violent crimes such as assault and armed robbery 78.57%; and problem of corruption and bribery 70.83%. It put the overall level of crime at 75% (this was the attempted crime index in 2012). In a comprehensive study on Nigeria, 11,518 Nigerians were interviewed by Chemical Legislation European Enforcement Network (CLEEN, 2012). They found out that three of every four Nigerians live in fear of experiencing violent crime occurrence (Adetula, 2013).

Crimes and Crime rates in Nigeria

The growth in urban crime rate in Nigeria is one of the major social problems facing the country in recent times (Femi *et al.*, 2015). According to Femi *et al.* (2015), the dominance of crime in developing countries like Nigeria increases the volatility of the issue, for it pyramids one fear upon others. They further maintain that the concentration of violent crimes in major urban centres worldwide is therefore heralded as an indicator of the breakdown of urban systems. In many urban centres of Nigeria today, criminal activities and violence are assuming dangerous tendencies as they threaten lives and property, the national sense of well-being and coherence, peace, social order and security, thus, reducing the citizens' quality of life (Ahmed, 2010).

Femi *et al.*, (2015), posit that over the years the rate of crime in Nigeria has been on the increase and these crimes are being carried out with more perfect sophistication. Fajemirokun, Adewale, Idowu, Oyewusi, and Maiyegun, (2006) argue that this has led to the formation of various vigilante groups, to combat crimes in some parts of the country. Nigeria has one of the highest crime rates in the world, as murder often accompanies minor burglaries, causing the rich Nigerians to live in high-security compounds (Femi *et al.*, 2015). According to Financial Times (2009), Police in some states are empowered to “shoot on sight” violent criminals. There is no disagreement from both macro and micro-level studies that the rate of crime in Nigeria has reached an unacceptable level (Femi *et al.*, 2015).

Ahmed (2010) posits that in many urban centres of Nigeria today, criminal activities and violence are assuming dangerous tendencies as they threaten lives and properties, the national sense of well-being and coherence, peace, social order and security, thus reducing the citizen quality of life. Many crime scenes and criminal activities have taken over Nigerian society. Many cities and rural areas have experienced crimes at various dimensions and degrees. Many losses have been counted and listed by the victims. Nwankwo and James (2016) in their study gave details of rates of crimes within the states and the Federal Capital city of the nation. According to them, criminal activities in Nigeria include armed robbery, cultism, kidnapping, rape, domestic violence, assassination, thuggery and hooliganism.

- i. **Armed robbery:** According to Nwankwo and James (2016), armed robbery has remained a major cause of death in Nigeria. Victims of such crime have cut across socio-economic status and occur mostly in major cities and states along transit points. Also, security personnel, civilians and robbers themselves have fallen victim to armed robbery. An overall 4,268 deaths occurred in 1682 armed robbery incidents nationwide (Nwankwo and James, 2016). There were reports of fatal armed robbery incidents in all the states in Nigeria including the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. However, fatalities varied by state. An emerging trend in armed robbery is bank attacks. On March, 26, several people including a branch bank manager and his Assistant were killed during an armed robbery incident in Oyo state. This attack came barely two months after a bank was attacked in Ondo and 22 people including policemen and civilians were killed. The most fatalities were reported in Delta (946 deaths), Lagos (819 deaths), Anambra (225 deaths), Ogun (184 deaths) and Zamfara (160 deaths). Gombe, Bayelsa, Jigawa, Kebbi and Plateau, on the other hand, enjoyed low fatalities from lethal armed robbery incidents. There were 13 deaths in Gombe, 16 in Bayelsa, 18 deaths in Jigawa and Kebbi respectively and 21 in Plateau. These statistics show that fewer fatal armed robbery incidents occur in the Northern part of Nigeria than their Southern counterparts (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Nwankwo and James further maintained that the trends of robbery fatalities in Nigeria between June 2006 and September 2015 show that there were reported 275 robbery incidents that culminated in 690- deaths in 2007. This marked the most fatal year of fatal robbery incidents within the period under review. The trend changed in the subsequent three years (2008-2010) with a downward trend. About 594 deaths occurred in 210 robbery incidents in 2008; another 360 deaths in 142 incidents in 2009 and 251 deaths in 145 incidents in 2010.

However, fatality trend has fluctuated between 2011 and 2015 (Nwankwo and James, 2016). In 2011, about 383 deaths occurred in 145 robbery incidents, 394 deaths in 151 incidents in 2012 and 432 deaths in 165 in 2013. The year 2014 marked a drop in robbery fatalities (374) from the previous year but still maintained an upward trend in the number of incidents with 168 incidents. However, with 320 deaths in 136 deaths within ten (10) months of 2015, one may argue for high incidents of armed robbery cases as well as an increase in the number of robbery fatalities (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

- ii. **Kidnapping:** According to Nwankwo and James (2016), kidnapping has remained one of the major crimes in the nation. Kidnapping has become a national phenomenon as the entire country is now a kidnapers' den. Ransom kidnapping and hostage-taking are no longer restricted to the Niger Delta area or South-South of Nigeria with reported cases in Lagos, Abuja, Benin City, Owerri, and now Kaduna and Kano. Nwankwo and James (2016), posit that kidnapping has spread to 22 states of the Federation, with a total of 457 deaths in 166 events. Akwa Ibom recorded the most cases of fatal kidnapping with 55 deaths, seconded by Lagos with 50 deaths, Delta with 44 deaths, Rivers with 25 deaths and Borno with 20 deaths. Four of these states are from the Southern Nigeria (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Victims of kidnapping according to Nwankwo and James (2016), span wide including security personnel as severally witnessed in Obingwa, Akwa Ibom state, kidnapped foreign and national residents and the kidnapers themselves. Often, ransom is paid to secure the release of the abductees. However, the incidence of kidnapping in Borno was perpetrated by

Boko Haram, an Islamic extremist group that busted into the limelight in 2009 (Nwankwo and James, 2016). In February 2013, scores of lives were reportedly lost in connection with the search for French hostages kidnapped by Boko Haram in Dikwa. There were instances where some women were kidnapped, raped and killed afterwards. For instance, a businessman Shola Olaseinde was kidnapped and killed by 5-gang fraudsters impersonating as women on a dating site in Rivers state. In 2010, another woman, Hyacinth Azu Nwangolo, Head of Economic Affairs, Rivers State Ministry of Women Affairs was abducted in her car and killed after ransom was not paid to secure her release. Another goring incident happened in Edo state in 2012 when two students of Federal Polytechnic, Auchi, Edo State, Henry Edewo and Emmanuel Isikhuime, kidnapped, raped and murdered a female student, one Mercy Peter also a student of the institution. They bury their victim in a forest. The victim, who was kidnapped on July 29, 2018, was killed four days later after she was serially raped by the suspects. They were also alleged to have continued to demand ransom from her parents after killing her (Nwankwo and James, 2016). While kidnapping thrived in some states, others recorded fewer fatalities and incidences of kidnapping. Such states include Benue, Bayelsa and Bauchi with 1 death respectively, Taraba and Ebonyi with 2 deaths each. There was only one incident of kidnapping that resulted in 1 death in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

The year 2013 was reported the most fatal with 80 deaths from 30 kidnap incidents (Nwankwo and James, 2016). There were fewer kidnap fatalities and incidents in 2014 as 53 deaths were recorded in 27 incidents. In 2010, 51 people were killed in 45 kidnap incidents and another 31 people were killed in 18 incidents in 2011. About 25 people were killed in 11 incidents in 2012 18 were killed in 8 incidents in 2009; 11 were killed in 2 events in 2006; 3 were killed in 3 events in 2007 and 2 were killed in 2 incidents in 2008. Between January and September 2015, 24 people have been killed in 15 kidnap incidents nationwide (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Security personnel were the most hit in the overall kidnap incidents in Nigeria (Nwankwo and James, 2016). About 621 security personnel comprising of police, soldiers, naval officers and secret service men were killed in the various kidnap incidents. This figure overshadowed the number of kidnappers and civilians killed. In Akwa Ibom state, security personnel were severely targeted and killed by kidnappers and their rifles were taken always for further attacks (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

- iii. Rape: Rape has been identified to be on the rise in many parts of the country (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Nwankwo and James further postulate that the world over; rape is regarded as a major crime against the helpless and popularly frowned upon. Some rapes have been fatal and such occurred in 25 states of the federation and FCT, Abuja (Nwankwo and James, 2016). A total of 147 women were raped to death in 56 incidents in these states. Lagos state recorded the highest rape fatalities with 35 deaths, Edo with 10, Ogun, Benue and Akwa Ibom states recorded 9 deaths respectively. There were a further 7 in Delta, 6 in Bayelsa, Kaduna and Ondo respectively and 5 in Ekiti, Enugu and Imo respectively (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Anambra, Ebonyi, Osun and Oyo states reported 4 deaths respectively and there were 3 deaths in Akwa Ibom, FCT, Abuja, Plateau and Rivers. Nasarawa and Zamfara reported 2 deaths while Cross Rivers and Niger reported one death. However, there were no reported fatal rape in 12 states including Adamawa, Borno, Gombe, Jigawa,

Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Sokoto, Taraba and Yobe (Nwankwo and James, 2016). The trend of rape fatalities and incidence between June 2006 and September 2015. About 27 females were killed in 2010, 25 in 2014, 15 in 2015 (January - September), 14 in 2013 and 13 in 2011 and 2012. Another 11 people were killed in 2009 and 2006 (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

- iv. **Assassination:** Assassination is a serious crime in Nigeria, and has been a major cause of fatal deaths in Nigeria (Nwankwo and James, 2016). About 676 persons were assassinated in 35 states in Nigeria and FCT, Abuja (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Assassinations are often targeted at prominent persons, especially politicians and perpetuated by thugs and hooligans. Many people were assassinated during general elections. Lagos state witnessed the most reported cases of assassinations with 172 deaths between June 2006 and September 2015. About 67 people were killed in Oyo state, 42 persons in Bauchi and 32 persons in Delta, Ogun and Rivers states respectively (Nwankwo and James, 2016). The assassinations mainly occurred at the different stages of the general election including the pre-, during, and post-election periods (Nwankwo and James, 2016). About 102 people were assassinated in 56 violent events in 2007, 118 persons in 43 events in 2011 and 115 persons in 44 events in 2015 (Nwankwo and James, 2016).
- iv. **Cultism:** According to Nwankwo and James (2016), cult-related activities abound in the nooks and crannies of our society, especially in institutions of higher learning. Worrisome it has become that such cult activities have been taken to secondary schools though not as pronounced as in the higher institutions. Cultism is rampant among teenagers and young adolescent youths (Nwankwo and James 2016). Cultism has created room for youths and teenagers to be involved in crimes and criminal activities across the nation. They further argued that casualties of cultism cut across innocent civilians, gang members and security personnel. Cult attacks in September (2015) saw the killing of 61 people in three states. In Rivers states, 20 persons were brutally murdered during a clash between Degbam and Barbeach Group said to be the armed wing of Islander. In Edo state, 25 people were killed in a cult clash between Manfight and Aiye (Neo Black Movement of Africa) over a supremacy battle (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Cultists also saw the killing of 16 people during a clash between 'Aiye' and 'Eiye' cult confraternities. A breakdown of the figures shows that there were 2363 deaths from cult-related activities in 28 states of the federation. Rivers state was most hit with cult killings with 765 deaths (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

There were 323 deaths in Lagos state, 306 in Edo, 202 in Delta, 104 in Bayelsa and 99 in Ogun (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Most affected states are from the Southern part of the country. On the contrary, the least affected states include Sokoto and Katsina with 1 death respectively, Plateau and Bauchi with 2 deaths respectively and Oyo with 4 deaths. The Oyo state remains the only Southern state that has relatively been free from cult-related killing. With the statistics, one can argue that there are fewer cult killings in the North than in the South of Nigeria (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Cohen and Felson (1979) developed the Routine Activity (RA) theory to explain why

crimes occur. RA theory employs a social explanation to explain seasonal oscillations in crime. It focuses on opportunities and risk, rather than on offender motivation, and is based on the idea that for an understanding of criminal behaviour, one needs to understand how individuals routinely use their time (Breetzke and Cohn, 2012). This theory postulates that individuals generally follow strict daily, weekly, and even monthly routines, which affects opportunities for crime and the risk of victimization (Brunsdon, Corcoran, Higgs, and Ware, 2009). Some of these routine activities are obligatory, with a reasonably fixed duration, and are difficult to change, such as work while other activities are discretionary such as socializing, and individuals have a greater amount of choice as to whether they will engage in these activities and when they will occur (Breetzke and Cohn, 2012).

Routine Activity (RA) theory also states that for a crime to occur, three elements must converge in time and space. These elements are motivated offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of a capable guardian against criminal behaviour (Cohen and Felson, 1979 cited in Wumi, Olanrewaju, and Abel, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The survey research method was adopted for this study because the research covers a large population which is infinite. The study area is Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom state. Eket Senatorial District consists of 12 local government areas which include; Eastern Obolo, Eket, Esit Eket, Ibeno, Ikot Abasi, Mbo, MkpateEnin, Okobo, Onna, Oron, UdungUko, and UrueOffong/Oruko local government areas. These local government areas make up the Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. Eket Senatorial District also known as Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District comprises 3 ethnic groupings in Akwa Ibom State. These ethnic groups include Ibibio, Oro, and Ekid. The local government areas that make up the Ibibio ethnic group in Eket Senatorial District include; Onna, Ikot Abasi, and Mkpate Enin. The local government areas that make up the Oro ethnic groups include; Oron, Mbo, Okobo, Obolo, UdungUko, and UrueOffong/Oruko. The targeted population of this study was the people in Eket Senatorial District, which is also, referred to as Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. The projected population of Eket Senatorial District, according to the Akwa Ibom State Demographic Dividend Profile (2018), as derived from the 2006 national population census (NPC, 2006) is 1,095,980. In determining the sample size, the researcher used the Alien Taro Yamane method. Yamane (1967) provides a simplified formula to calculate sample size. Therefore, the sample size of this study was 400 and was randomly selected from each of the local government areas within Eket Senatorial District. The instrument used in this study was the questionnaire. The data collected in this study are descriptively presented using the percentage, charts and graphs methods. Analysis was done according to research objectives.

RESULT

Question 1: What types of criminal activities are practised by youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State?

Figure 1: Line Graph showing responses on the existence of crimes in Eket Senatorial District

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2024)

Figure 1 shows the kinds of crimes experienced by the people of Eket Senatorial District as agreed by responses through the questionnaire as collected by the researcher. The figures show that in Eket Senatorial District, burglary has the highest number of responses with 373 (93.2%). This is followed by armed robbery with 356 (89.0%). The next crime with the highest number of responses from the study participants is Assault with 103 (25.8%). Murder is next with 95 (23.7%) of responses from the study participants, kidnapping follows with 72 (18.0%) of the responses, rape is next with 21 (5.2%) of responses, assassination follows with 15 (3.8%), and the crime with least responses is man slaughter with 11 (2.8%). This implies that people have experienced burglary crimes more than any other crime in Eket Senatorial District.

Question 2: What are the rates of criminal practices of youths in Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State?

Figure 2: Line Graph showing the rate of crime/s committed by youths in Eket Senatorial District as experienced by the people

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork (2024)

Figure 2 shows the crime rates experienced by the people of Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. Out of the 400 responses from the shared and collected questionnaires, assault is the most frequently experienced crime with 346 (77.5%) of the study participants agreeing to that. The next crime that is experienced more often in Eket Senatorial District as reported by the study participants is armed robbery with 310 (77.5%) responses of the study participants. This is followed by kidnapping with 202 (50.5%) responses by the study participants in Eket Senatorial District. The next crime which is often experienced in Eket Senatorial District as reported by the study participants is burglary with 133 (33.3%). This is followed by murder with 25 (6.2%) which is a less often experienced crime as reported by the study participants. This is followed by rape with 24 (6%) of the responses of the study participants. Assassination is the next with 22 (5.5%) of the responses of the study participants. The last with the lesser rate of experience by the people of Eket Senatorial District is man slaughter with 18 (4.5%).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Youths in Akwa Ibom State are facing similar economic, political and social situations as related to other parts of Nigeria, especially in the South-East and South-South geo-political regions of Nigeria. The continuous struggle for employment and other means of survival by the Akwa Ibom youths have contributed to criminal activities which are experienced by the people of Akwa Ibom State, especially within the Eket Senatorial District. These emerging findings satisfy Uyang *et al.* (2016), who maintained that youth involvement in criminal activities in Nigeria has assumed a worrisome dimension in recent times. Adebayo (2013) also maintained that youth's involvement in criminality has become an integral part of the nation's daily life. In this study, emerging findings were made and these are summarized under the following sub-headings:

Emergence from the findings of the study has it that some Eket Senatorial District youths engage in criminal activities like armed robbery, kidnapping, burglary, rape, assault, murder, manslaughter, assassination, etc. The finding is in agreement with the position of Adebayo (2013) who maintained that the season of discontent has special ramifications for a nation with unemployed millions of youths, and the net effect has been a tragic precipitation of violent crimes: assault, burglary, extortion kidnapping etc. The findings also reveal that the type of crimes which the youths in Eket Senatorial District mostly engage in are burglary, armed robbery, assault, kidnapping, murder and rape. According to Nwankwo and James (2016), kidnapping has remained one of the major crimes in the nation. Kidnapping has become a national phenomenon as the entire country is now a kidnappers' den. In 2011, about 383 deaths occurred in 145 robbery incidents, 394 deaths in 151 incidents in 2012 and 432 deaths in 165 in 2013. The year 2014 marked a drop in robbery fatalities (374) from the previous year but still maintained an upward trend in the number of incidents with 168 incidents (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Emergence from the findings of the study has it that some Akwa Ibom youths engage in criminal activities like armed robbery, kidnapping, burglary, rape, assault, murder, manslaughter, assassination, etc as agreed with the position of Adebayo (2013) who maintained that the season of discontent has special ramifications for a nation with unemployed millions of youths, and the net effect has been a tragic precipitation of violent crimes: assault, burglary, extortion and kidnapping etc. findings also reveals that the type of

crimes which the youths in Eket Senatorial District mostly engage in are burglary, armed robbery, assault, kidnapping, murder and rape.

Discovery from the study shows that some crimes are often practised by the youths of Eket Senatorial District. Emergence of the analysis of data shows that the people of Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State experience more assault than any other crime. This shows that the rate of assault committed by the youths of Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State is higher than that of any other crime committed by the youths of the senatorial district. This finding agrees with Esiri's (2016) position which maintained that crime has become a hot debate in the agenda of most nations yet it does not seem to be on the decline, rather it is on the increase. Findings also reveal that manslaughter is the least experienced crime among the people of Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. This implies that the crime with the lowest rate of occurrence as committed by the youths of Eket Senatorial District is manslaughter.

CONCLUSION

The growth in urban crime rate in Nigeria is one of the major social problems facing the country in recent times. Nearly everywhere and around Nigerian cities, the atmosphere is inflicted with criminal menace being wrecked by some criminal-minded youths on law-abiding members of the Nigerian public. Some criminally minded Akwa Ibom youths engage in criminal activities like armed robbery, kidnapping, burglary, rape, assault, murder, manslaughter, assassination, etc. The youths in Eket Senatorial District mostly engage in burglary, armed robbery, assault, kidnapping, murder and rape.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are made from the findings of this research:

1. The government should equip the Nigerian Police and other security organizations for effective crime policing in Nigeria.
2. The government should encourage private sector expansion to have more job created for the teaming unemployed youths within every region of the nation.
3. The government should improve the economic condition of the nation to bring about an improved standard of living for the masses.

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